

SOCIAL SCIENCIES

FORMING PROFESSIONAL SOCIAL WORK IN THE CONTEXT OF POSTMODERNISM DISCOURSES: EVALUATION OF DYNAMICS FROM 1991 TO 2000

Firsov M.V.

Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor, Deputy Dean of the Faculty of Psychology for Scientific Work of the Russian State Social University (st. Wilhelm Pika, 4, build. 1, Moscow, 129226)

Chernikova A.A.

Junior Researcher, Institute for Demographic Research – Branch of the Federal Center of Theoretical and Applied Sociology of the Russian Academy of Sciences (IDR FCTAS RAS) (119333, Moscow, Fotieva st., 6, build. 1))

Abstract

The article is devoted to the analysis of the formation of professional social work from the beginning of the 90s to 2000. The changes are connected with the processes of de-Sovietization of Russian society. Social protection in the 90s was implemented as a project of the new ruling elites in the discourses of postmodernism.

Keywords: social work, platform 1.0, postmodernism, postmodernization, clinical vector

A new stage in the formation of professional social work begins in the early 1990s, and it was associated with the processes of de-Sovietization of Russian society. The process of de-Sovietization was carried out in the logic of postmodernism, in the context of the processes of globalization, the destruction of “the traditional way of life, the chaos of financial markets and public goods”[29].

The American sociologist Z. Bauman, defining the essence of postmodernism in the life of society, from our point of view, quite accurately reflected its socio-psychological state, which is characteristic not only for Western civilization, but also for the Russian society of social transformations of the 90s: “... the period of postmodernism is carried out How is life during a crisis. Postmodern thinking is aware that there are problems in human life and society that have no good solutions; that there are only winding roads that cannot be straightened... that there are doubts that cannot be eliminated by legislation from existence; that there are moral sufferings which cannot be appeased by any arguments of reason”[26].

Comprehending the social and political reforms of the late twentieth century in Russia, it can be noted that the strategies in the discourses of postmodernism were implemented in various areas, and the characteristic features of these transformations were numerous projects that determined the essence of the transitive state of both social relations and social institutions [22].

Economic, political, and ideological uncertainty made its own adjustments to the management policy of the ruling elites at all levels, in all segments of the economy, including the emerging system of social protection.

Social protection in the 90s was implemented as a project of the new ruling elites in the discourses of postmodernism, in this context, social work developed in several directions simultaneously:

- professional activity, within the framework of the new state project of "social protection",

- the field of knowledge, in the paradigm of "projects of post-Marxist knowledge" in the narratives of the humanities,

- the direction of education as a project of "social education" in the context of the Bologna processes.

In this most complex crucible of various social, educational and professional projects, a “new image” of the national paradigm of social work was formed.

The system of social protection in the Russian Federation in the new socio-political conditions was formed in a situation of liberal reform, and there were simply no direct ways out of the "socialist paradise", as well as the entrance to it in the past, at this historical stage.

During this period, the ruling elites chose a course for the modernization of the economy, transferring it to the “market rails”, which was connected with the course of privatization of state institutions and forms of ownership.

The modernization of the economy in the logic of postmodernism expanded the strategies of capital accumulation, and the "architects of modernization" were not limited only to privatizations of the production sector, minerals, modernization also covered the social sphere, its segments such as education and healthcare.

Social protection will be included in these processes later, and not because the processes of capitalization in Russia were implemented on the "humanistic principles of democratic capitalism", but because the process of marginalization has engulfed the entire Russian society, both the working population and pensioners and disabled people in the care of the state and dependent children who have been under his constant patronage for decades.

This aspect of economic reforms determined the specifics of both social security models and the practice of social work in the Russian Federation, which was characterized by:

- variety of implementation of assistance practices,

- the breadth of practical boundaries for the use of support technologies,
- understanding of the "multidimensional realities" with which professionals had to interact,
- "relativity of truths",

From the point of view of the British researcher F. Williams, it determined the essence of postmodern approaches [31]. The "multidimensionality of realities", the variety of social problems faced by professionals, required the discovery of various types and types of social protection institutions. And if at the previous stage social work was formalized as an activity for social service at home for pensioners and the disabled, in selected territories, then in the 90s not only the vector of practice, but also the scope of coverage of professional activities in the regions of the Russian Federation changed significantly.

As studies show, in all 86 constituent entities of the Russian Federation, from 1994 to 2006, social protection institutions were opened for various categories of citizens. Families, street children, the unemployed, migrants, and other numerous categories of the needy, determined by the current legislation, were included in the scope of social work. The massive approach to helping those in need has led to the fact that the number of social protection institutions in the first decade of the formation of the social service system has increased by 22.5 times [4].

The decisions that were made during this period may have been optimal in the here and now situation, but they were not the most effective in the situation that inevitably occurs over time.

During the period under review, the construction of a solidary society in the paradigm of postmodernism in Western social states had complex, pragmatic and more "economical" models of mutual assistance than in the Russian Federation.

At the heart of helping strategies in Western countries, the search for models of "easing the burden on the budget of the public sector" was implemented, by redistributing this burden on partners and actors of mutual assistance from other sectors, including the non-state sector.

In the process of developing social work in the world community, by that time such strategies as the deinstitutionalization of social security institutions, the organization of self-help models, the transfer of state social protection institutions to outsourcing, the development of the sector of non-profit services, charitable organizations, the activation of civil society through the practice of volunteering, developing professional support for those in need through the institutions of the Churches, attracting funds and professionals from foreign associations to work with certain categories of clients, including "preserving the traditional family model with care services" [28].

Russia followed its "traditional path" of creating models of a solidarity society by increasing services and building ever new social institutions through the public sector, which was typical of the previous ruling elites, who had been implementing the decisions of party congresses for decades [1,5]

The project "professional social work" had another feature, in addition to the institutionalization of social protection institutions.

The implemented models of social solidarity in the discourses of the ideologemes of postmodernism in this period were characterized by radical individualism.

And if at the stage of modernism, at the beginning of the 20th century, collectivist approaches dominated in identifying those in need, as was the case with the proletariat in Western countries, or as we observed in the early years of the formation of Soviet power in Russia, where not only the proletariat, but also the poorest Since the peasantry, invalids of the civil and imperialist wars had preferences for assistance from the authorities [23], then in this historical time, preference for assistance was determined at the local and individual level.

The difference between the ongoing social reforms of the 90s, from the social reforms of the 20s, was that at the end of the 20th century, social security was not so much the right to receive assistance from "oppressed social communities and groups", an act of realizing historical justice, but rather compensation to individuals and local communities for the lack of "good decisions" in reforming society.

In this regard, the social security policy was associated with the phenomena of extreme relativism, which actually constituted the focus of social work in the context of social security in the discourses of postmodernism, so the collectivist communist models of "universal happiness" were replaced by technologies of individual therapy of an individual case.

The conduct of social policy in the discourses of postmodernism, the solution of clients' problems on the basis of individual rather than collective identity, allowed the ruling elites to consider existing problems not from the standpoint of "concepts of helping the poor", but in "concepts of helping the poor", not from the standpoint of "social inequality", and from the standpoint of "individual insecurity", thus, the ideologemes of human rights were replaced by ideologemes of counteracting the marginalization of society, strategies of assistance and support were implemented from these principles.

However, despite the fact that in this period, international and European banks are actively pursuing a policy of lending to the "modernization of Russian society", and not so much the Russian economy, the ruling elites are gradually developing certain ideas about the need to reduce the growth rate of social institutions and regulate social benefits. -vulnerable groups, both in terms of numbers and their intended purpose, which actually caused the further introduction of the law on the monetization of benefits [20].

This decision was "pushed by a number" of socio-economic and socio-political factors.

On the one hand, the growth of social institutions, almost a 20-fold increase, solved the problems of the needy population in the situation "here and now", but over time, all these institutions had to require huge investments to keep them in working condition, which inevitably led to crisis situation in social security that the

authorities faced in the 80s, but only the emerging situation would have had a larger scale of crisis manifestations.

On the other hand, the use of only state funding in the development of the social sphere in a situation of total privatization, labor strikes, the movement of troops from Western Europe, the conduct of wars in the North Caucasus would inevitably lead to a reduction in social spending, and the curtailment of "intensive differentiated social programs" and searches for other "projects of financing the social sphere".

Social institutions during this period provided assistance and support on the basis of the current legislation, which determined social groups, in accordance with state priorities. At the same time, the state regulated the situations in which it was included in the matter of assistance and support, localized difficult life situations through the professional community of social workers.

Individual service, individual service, sanctioned, as in health care institutions, not only socially deviant forms of behavior acceptable from the point of view of social norms, but also any individual forms of protest and "civil disobedience".

Through the tools of "social security", "tolerance", "empathic listening", "medial technologies", "problem solving technologies" and other personality-oriented assistance tools, social workers allowed clients to realize their individual aggressive behavior in situations that were conditioned as environmental and individual-group factors.

The main goal of the actions of professionals in this context is the correction of the psycho-socio-emotional state of a person and the prevention of the development of individual forms of protest into mass forms of disorganization based on collective forms of solidarity.

It can be noted that the functions of "supervision-correction" were implemented not only by the institutions of correction, as was observed in previous eras, but also by the institutions of socialization, support and

support, which was carried out in the context of the modernization of society.

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